

International Journal of Dental Anthropology IJDA

ISSN 0124-7336 (www.ijda.net)

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Inter. J. Dental Anthropol. 1: 5-15 (2000)

ID: ijda00002

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10471636>

DENTAL PATHOLOGY AND DIET DURING THE IV MILLENNIUM BC IN CIUDAD REAL (SPAIN)

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Resumen

En este trabajo se presenta el estudio bioantropológico de un enterramiento colectivo datado en el neolítico final (posiblemente calcolítico) hallado en un abrigo montañoso en el Cerro Ortega, localidad de Villanueva de la Fuente (*Ciudad Real, España*). La demografía del yacimiento pone de manifiesto la existencia de un número mínimo de 19 individuos, 12 adultos (5 mujeres y 7 hombres) y 7 niños.

Se ha llevado a cabo un estudio de indicadores paleonutricionales. Entre los resultados paleoestomatológicos destaca un grado de desgaste oclusal leve-moderado, un 6.4 % de caries, un 21.3 % de hipoplasia del esmalte, un 56.4 % de cálculo y un 63.7 % de enfermedad periodontal. También se ha llevado a cabo un estudio preliminar de los restos faunísticos, destacando la presencia de animales herbívoros salvajes: *oryctolagus cuniculus* (conejo) y *capra hircus* (cabra), así como fracturas de hueso fresco posiblemente de manipulación alimenticia humana. El análisis de oligoelementos indica que dicha población tuvo una dieta mixta agrícola con aporte medio de proteínas animales (ratio Sr/Ca(c)=0.843 y ratio Zn/Ca=0.397). También se destaca la presencia de un caso de síndrome osteoarqueológico poroso, indicativo de déficit nutricional.

Abstract

This work is about the bioanthropological study of a collective interment, dated from the Neolithic Period (possibly Calcolithic), located in a Mountainous Shelter in Ortega Hill, Villanueva de la Fuente (*Ciudad Real, Spain*). The demography of the site makes clear the existence of a minimum number of 19 individuals, 12 adults (5 women and 7 men) and 7 children.

A study of paleonutritional indicators has been carried

out. Among the paleostomatological results, a degree of a slight-moderate occlusive abrasion is underlined, a 6,4% of dental caries, a 21,3% of enamel hypoplasia, a 56,4% of dental calculus, and a 63,7% of periodontal illness. A preliminary study of the faunal remains has also been carried out, underlining the presence of wild herbivorous animals: *oryctolagus cuniculus* (rabbit) and *capra porcus* (goat), as well as fractures of fresh bones, probably as a result of human food handling. The analysis of oligoelements shows that this population had an agricultural mixed diet with half contribution of animal proteins (ratio Sr/Ca (c) = 0.843 and ratio Zn/Ca = 0.397). The presence of a porous osteoarcheological syndrome case, indicative of a nutritional deficit, is also evident.

The Archaeological Context

In June 1997, Archaeological Excavations Management Company (GEA) carried out an emergency archaeological excavation in Ortega Hill Slope, located in the outskirts of Villanueva de la Fuente, Ciudad Real (Spain). (See figure 1). There, a collective in-cave tomb was found by chance. Due to an erosion produced by a storm, human remains partially came out to the surface.

The excavation was subsidized by the Culture Management of Education, and Culture Advisory Board of Castilla, La Mancha, and has allowed us to discover an interesting way of burying a human group who lived in the river valley of Villanueva de la Fuente.

The archaeological date, obtained from the recovered material and funeral trousseau, situates that necropolis by the IV millennium BC, and it could be a population from the late Neolithic Period or maybe from the transition to the Calcolithic.

The interments were distributed anarchically. It was

even very difficult to establish an anatomical link among many of the skeletons distributed in 29 stratigraphical units. The preliminary archaeological study has made clear that the human remains seem to have suffered a kind of handling because there were some stratigraphical units in which there were almost exclusively cranial remains, and others where there were only bones corresponding to extremities. However there is a possibility that this distribution may have taken place due to *tapho-edaphologic* phenomena.

Next to the human remains, a lot of faunal remains and trousseau elements (arrow points, necklace beads, bond spatulas and punches, silex sheets...) were found.

The whole human and faunal remains were placed in the Forensic Anthropology and Paleopathology Laboratory, Legal Medicine Teaching Unit at University of Valencia (Spain), where a full bioanthropological study has been carried out during the period 1998 – 2000.

Objective

The objective of this work is to present the results obtained from the study of Paleonutritional Health Indicators, and to be able to give objective data about the buccodental health and diet state of this human group.

Materials

The mandible and jaw remains, isolated dental pieces, the cranial and postcranial remains, belonging to a minimum number of 19 individuals were studied. A preliminary study of the faunal remains was also carried out.

Methodology

The methodology used in this work follows a research line whose conceptual synthesis is as follows:

Paleonutritional Health Indicators

The reconstruction of the feeding and the nutritional state of ancient populations requires an interdisciplinary detailed study that involves numerous areas of knowledge dedicated to the investigation of antiquity and man. This extensive approach is precisely what allows us to give enough consensus information to issue an exact and collective answer about the nutritional state of a given population.

There are several sciences that may participate in paleonutritional studies and specially, the information from auxiliary sciences of archaeology has to be wisely used. Among those sciences the physics and biology anthropology as well as the Paleopathology play a leading role.

Figure 1. Geographical Location of the Collective Interment

In this work, the whole of the paleonutritional health indicators, studied from Paleoanthropology, paleostomatology and Paleopathology, are researched. We are not going to study in deep the archaeological markers, unrelated to our study field. However, at the end of this paper, we will present the preliminary results of the faunal study.

Paleonutritional Indicators Concept

In the specialized literature we often find expressions such as “environmental stress indicators” or “environmental pressure indicators” when referring to some skeletal markers that leave their signs in the bones, due, in many cases, to the excess or shortage of feeding resources.

When many authors talk about the nutrition analysis of an ancient population from the skeletal remains, they refer to the “stress factors” to which the given population has been exposed to. If we investigate in many of this markers, what they are really reporting is irect and/or indirect data about the population nutritional state.

For this reason, we think it would be convenient to start talking about the paleonutritional health indicators and abandon the expression “stress” when referring to those “nutritional stress indicators”. Apart from this, there are exclusive indicators of pathological “stress” and the occupational “stress” (*paleoccupational* or *paleoprofessional* indicators) subject to other conceptual and methodological revisions. Nevertheless, new investigations we have carried out clearly aim to show that certain paleonutritional indicators are pathological indicators at the same time. It is to say that there are mixed indicators, or of malnutritional and pathological synergy.

In the light of the foregoing, the paleonutritional

health indicator can be defined as follows:

“It is a paleoanthropological and/or paleopathological population sanitary marker by means of which a relation of proportionality between two variables, subject of study, is established. In a direct, quantitative, and qualitative way, it permits to know the nutritional health level; and in an indirect way, to infer the social and economical development degree of that population.”

For a better understanding of the suggested concept, let's divide it into the following points:

1. It is a sanitary marker; indirectly, an economical and sociocultural one.
2. It may be either anthropological (morphometric, chemical, radiological, demographic) or paleopathological data.
3. It always establishes a proportional relation between two variables: the anthropological and/or paleopathological data; and its corresponding correlation with a kind of feeding, a sort of feeding economy, some nutritional deficits, etc.
4. In a direct way, the nutritional level is indicated quantitatively (e.g. the caries or periodontal illness effect, a certain concentration of Sr, Zn, Mg, etc...or the corrected signs of Sr/Ca, Zn/Ca, etc...), or qualitatively (e.g. the degree of occlusive dental abrasion, typology of dental micro striation, presence of enamel hypoplasia, of *cribra orbitalia*, and porous or a kind of sieve syndrome, etc...). That is, if the population was poor or well fed, and if it had a meat or vegetarian diet, etc.
5. Indirectly, it permits to know the kind of feeding and economical resources as well as social development.

The requirements that every paleonutritional indicator has to comply with are the same as those required to any sanitary indicator:

1. It has to be easily obtained from bone remains.
2. It has to be representative. This may be the major problem we have to face when analyzing an indicator of this sort. It means that the representativity of the sample is limited to the available sample. Therefore the data has to be evaluated in terms of the same sample which in some cases may be representative of a historically dated population group, but it may not be so in other cases. What we want to say is that a paleonutritional indicator can be or not to be representative in relation to the bone collection under analysis.
3. Its diagnosis, observation and calculation have to be simple. In this sense, there are

easy-to-value indicators, like the *cribra orbitalia*, and there are other difficult-to-value indicators like the quantification of oligoelements.

4. It has to be valid. That is, the indicator has to directly or indirectly tell us about the nutritional state of the population under study

5. It has to be specific, of a feeding type or of a nutritional deficit.

6. It has to be accepted by the scientific community as an indicator of the nutritional level, and of the conditions and the population's life quality. Thus, in order to propose the inclusion of new indicators of this kind, it is necessary for them “to be sufficiently solid as for the things they can tell or inform”.

7. It is understood that every new indicator has to be perfectly reproducible in an experimentally. This is probably the most difficult aspect to accomplish in Paleopathology. It also makes that the study of new indicators of paleonutritional health has motivated us to continue with the almost non-existent experimental Paleopathology, we defend. A very good example of this situation is the definition of a new osteorchaologic syndrome, indicator of paleonutritional health: the porous syndrome that we will later present in this paper.

Classification of Paleonutritional Indicators

It is not our purpose to do an exhaustive revision of each paleonutritional health indicator but to try to systematize them (Polo, M.; Miquel, M. and Villalain, J.D., 1999b).

Most of the paleonutritional information comes from the observation of dental pieces and their pathology. Without a doubt, the tooth is the most directly related to diet skeletal indicator (the feeding habit). As a consequence, the Classical Physics Anthropology, since its beginnings, has used different buccodental pathologies as its principal indicators. But at this moment in time, this science we now call Biological Anthropology is supported by other methods and disciplines, like Paleopathology, to go deeper in the study of these and other markers.

From a structural point of view we can classify the paleonutritional indicators' collection in four groups (see Table 1):

1. Morphological Indicators: paleopathological and anthropometric.
2. Biochemical Indicators.
3. Radiological Indicators.
4. Paleodemographic Indicators.

Those markers subject to macroscopically and microscopically analysis are included within the group of

morphological indicators. They can also be paleopathological and anthropological indicator. The collective of buccodental pathological indicators are underlined within the first group. At the same time, they could be subdivided in direct indicators (caries, tartar, enamel hypoplasia, periodontal illness, occlusive dental wear, dental micro striation pattern, phytoliths typology, etc...), and indirect indicators (ante mortem abscess and dental loss). Other paleopathological indicators are *cribra orbitalia*, the criboso or porous syndrome, the periostitis, hyperostosis, "premature" osteoporosis, hypovitaminosis D, etc... Cranial thickness slimming, diaphysary flattening, height, cortical thickness, skeletal robustness and dental measurements, among others, are the most important anthropometric indicators (indirectly, indicators of the population growth and development).

The group of biochemical indicators is formed by the levels of some bones' inorganic and organic elements. The quantification of oligoelements or draught elements, and the corresponding corrected indexes, with themselves in other bed trophic levels (Sr/Ca, Zn, Ba, Fe, Mg, etc...), allow us to know meat ingest and diet patterns (agricultural, vegetarian, mixed or pastoral). In addition, the organic part of the bone from bony collagen, permits to analyze stable isotopes from carbon and nitrogen and distinguish consumption profiles and food groups.

The group of radiological indicators consists of a collection of nutritional health markers, only objectionable from readings of radiological plaques. We are not going to include within this group, those pathologies whose diagnose is confirmed through the radiology. That is to say that here we are going to mention the signs which are exclusively radiographically valuable. Among them:

1. The Harris Lines. They are horizontal and transverse lines of bony density, situated in shafts of long bones near the metaphysics. They are mainly observed in tibia, but also in femur, metacarpals and metatarsals. The study is about the growing delaying lines that last forever. They are directly related to the enamel hypoplasia presence. The presence of these lines directly related to hyponutritional level, maternal nutrition deficit during the gestation, precocious weaning, hypovitaminosis A, infectious processes during the childhood (measles, grippe, varicella, pneumonia ...), etc.
2. The Looser Milkman lines. They are radio transparent bands, perpendicular to the cortical, which appear in osteomalacia (Vitamin D deficit).
3. Radiological signs in the scurvy (Hypovitaminosis C). Apart from the typical morphologically diagnosable costal rosary in the scurvy, a valuable radiographic signs se-

ries, is valuable at three typically characterized levels: diaphysary level (osteoporosis, cortical thinness, periosteal detachment, late subperiosteal hematomas and microfractures); metaphysary level (the Frankel's Line, dense and white because of calcium heap, due to a cartilage slow growth, and the line of Pelken, hyperclear and which constitutes a lax conjunctive tissue zone that has ossified out of time); and epiphysary level (nucleus "in soap bubble" and late epiphysary detachments).

4. Rachitis Radiological Signs. Nutritional rachitis, due to a poor in calcium and/or phosphorus diet, and a Vitamin D deficit, causes a series of characteristic radiological signs: deformity in metaphysary cup (metaphysary widening); frayed metaphysary growth line; delay in ossification centers' mineralization at an epiphysary level that is further from the growth line; osteoporosis, periosteal unfolding that in fact is a hyperplasia and periosteal osteoid deposit at a diaphysary level,

Finally, we find the Paleodemographic indicators group. It may be the most heterogeneous group from the four. In this, paleoepidemiological data (with reference to the pathology found in the studied population: percentages, frequencies, etc...) and Paleodemographic data (mortality rate, population growth, infantile - juvenile individuals rate, etc...) are integrated. These indicators indirectly tell us if the feeding resources were important or deficient; the incidence of infectious illnesses and/or nutritional deficits during childhood, among other aspects.

Results

The following are the study results of some paleonutritional indicators mentioned before. We have already published some preliminary results, complemented now with this work (Polo-Cerdá, M *et al* 1999a).

Buccodental Morphological Paleonutritional Indicators

Material

A total of 211 dental pieces have been studied. Almost the half (97) were isolated. As pieces, we have considered fragments of crown and root as well as isolated dental germs. The isolated pieces have been separated because of their location and dental group they belong to (see Table 2).

To the study, a macroscopic and metric method has been used. The following classifications have been applied:

-Holly Smith establishes 8 degrees for dental

abrasion (from 1 to 8), from minor to major affectation.
 -Brothwell distinguishes among light, middle, and considerable, both tartar and bone loss for dental calculus and alveolar bone loss.

As for enamel hypoplasia and caries, its presence or absence is indicated.

The alveolar bone decrease is only studied in pieces *in situ*. We have considered that the study of such a process through indirect signs in isolated pieces was not adequate because of their deterioration.

Finally, we have to say that in the study of the previous parameters we have not taken into account dental germs. If they were counted, they could falsify the percentages. This study is about non-erupted pieces; therefore, abrasion is null as well as the possibility of finding dental calculus or caries. These processes are found after the eruption, except for enamel hypoplasia that is stuck during tooth formation. This could be the only alteration in which all the pieces, even the out-breaks, would be considered. We have also despised them for these calculations because it may be necessary to consider all the dental germs, including those *in situ*; an impossible fact without breaking/destroying the jaws.

We have also despised three small root pieces because they have not been identified.

Results

The dental alterations that provide the most information about the nutritional state are presented.

The dental alterations which are most related to diet are caries, dental calculus, abrasion and enamel hypoplasia. The first three inform about the diet after the pieces eruption; the fourth provides information about the development periods of this tooth, and the individual in general.

Abrasion

Abrasion appears in both deciduous and permanent dentition. After assign a determined abrasion degree for each piece, they were grouped by light, moderate, or severe affectation. We consider light abrasion in the degrees 1, 2, and 3; moderate, 4 and 5; and severe, 7 and 8 (see Table 3).

A 43,6% of the permanent pieces (71) has a light affectation, percentage similar to the pieces with moderate abrasion (45,4%). Meanwhile, there are few teeth with severe abrasion (13,5%).

We did not find any deciduous pieces with severe abrasion. The moderate abrasion represents the 36% in this dentition, and the light, a 64%.

The majority of the studied teeth represent a light or moderate abrasion; there are few pieces with abrasion of 6, 7, or 8 degree. This could be due to, among other factors, the fact that it is a young population.

Caries

Only a 6,4% of the studied pieces show this pathology associated with multiple etiological factors. Among them, the refined carbon hydrate consumption is precisely outstanding in permanent teeth (7 *in situ* and 3 isolated), and in deciduous teeth (0 *in situ* and 2 isolated). (See Table 4).

Dental Calculus

It consists of a calcareous salts apposition, mainly in the neck, although it tends to cover the crown until it reaches the occlusive edge, in the most severe cases. In our study, it is found in a 56,4% of the sample. It is surprising that any of the worn-out teeth presented tartar, although it is present in the 65% of the permanent teeth, in a light affectation degree. It is necessary to take precautionary measures with the figures referred to the absence of dental calculus because this deposits could be detached postmortem (See Table 5).

INDICATORS	TIPOLOGY - FEATURES
MORPHOLOGICS	Buccodentals: Directs: Caries, Calculus, Enamel hypoplasia, Periodontal disease, Dental wear, Microstriation dental pattern, Phytolits tipology. Indirects: Abscess and Antemortem tooth loss. Cribra orbitalia, Porotic hiperostosis and criboso osteoarchaeologic syndrome. Paleopathologies: osteoarchaeologic syndrome of raquitism, scurvy, periostitis, etc... Anthropometrics: slimming of cranial thickness, diaphysiaric flattening, height, cortical thickness, skeletal strength, etc...
BIOQUIMICS	Oligoelements (Sr, Zn, Ba, Fe, Mg, etc...). Estable isotopes
RADIOLOGICS	Harris lines. Radiologic signals of hipovitaminosis D. Radiologic signals of hipovitaminosis C. Radiologic signals of raquitism.
PALEODEMOGRAPHICS	Mortality rates of perinatal, infantile, juvenile and adult. Growth rates and Population Development.

Table 1. Classification of Paleonutritional Health Indicators

Reduction of the Alveolar Bone

It is about a periodontal illness indicator, present in a 63,7% of teeth *in situ*. It has been observed in 65 permanent (67,7% of them), and in 7 deciduous. As it can be seen, it is a frequent process but in a light-medium degree (See Table 6).

Enamel Hypoplasia

It is about an amelogenesis delaying that is generally expressed in a furrow form, more-or-less strong. It is associated with nutritional lack during the dental development phase.

It is considered an “environmental stress” indicator. In the population under study, it appears in a 21,3% of the pieces: in permanent teeth: 21 *in situ* and 19 precisely isolated (See Table 4).

Dental Loss during Lifetime

We have detected only 11 cases of alveolar hole reabsorption that shows a tooth loss during lifetime.

Abscesses

It is about an infectious process not so frequent in the population under study. An abscess with buccal drainage in a first left inferior molar has been detected (See Figure 2). A less-serious one is present in a second left superior molar. Any signs of this have been seen in infantile remains.

Other Morphological Paleonutritional Indicators: *cribra orbitalia* and porous osteoarchaeological syndrome.

A presence of bilateral *cribra orbitalia* in a sub-adult individual has been detected.

			IN SITU	ISOLATED	TOTAL
PERMANENTS	molars	upper	22	6	29
		lower	18	2	20
	premolars	upper	15	6	21
		lower	12	8	20
	canines	upper	9	8	17
		lower	4	3	7
	incisors	upper	6	17	23
		lower	10	17	27
DECIDUALS	Molars Canines Incisors	13	7	20	
		3	1	4	
		1	0	1	
GERMENS		19	19		
ROOT FRAGMENTS		3	3		

Table 2. Identification of the Studied Dental Material

It is about a multiple microperforator lesion present in the orbit roof and is a consequence of a venous hypervascularization, associated with a bone medulla hyperplastic and hypertrophy. *Cribra orbitalia* is sometimes associated with a porous hyperostosis that usually affects the parietal. We have not verified it after have analyzed more than 120 skeletal dated from the Neolithic until today though this is a very rare association. On the contrary, there is an evident association between the presence of *cribra orbitalia* and *cribra femur*, such as the skeleton of this population. This fact lets us think that we are in the presence of a new paleopathological syndrome which may require the research attention in the future of all the paleopathologists (Miquel, M.; Polo, M. and Villalain, J.D., 1996).

We are not going to completely examine the whole etiopathogenia of this lesion, but we want to point out that we know about the *cribra orbitalia* and its association with other porous phenomena.

	DENTAL WEAR		
	slight	Moderate	severe
Permanents Isolated	31	28	11
Permanents in situ	40	46	11
Deciduals Isolated	6	2	0
Deciduals in situ	10	7	0
Percentage	46,3	44,2	11,7

Table 3. Results of the Occlusive Surface Abrasion Study

The archaeological syndrome (following the concept stated by Thillaud, 1992) *criboso* (Miquel; Polo and Villalain, 1999b) or porous “is defined by the presence of *cribra orbitalia* in infantile-juvenile individuals (>3 and <18 years old) symmetric *cribra femoral* in femurs, *hyperplatinemic* or *platinemic* and variable symmetric humeral *cribra*”.

As it is well stated by Gonzalez (1999 a and b), these porous associations “could be just revealing that all the indicators are valid” and correspond to a similar situation.

Porous or *cribosas* lesions (orbital, femoral, humeral and probably the rest of the localizations) constitute those very thing lesions or anatomic-pathologic entities with similar macroscopic, microscopic and radiographic characteristics, establishing an association statistically significant, and giving the possibility of being grouped under the mentioned syndrome (See Figure 3).

In all these porous localizations, there is a diploic hypertrophy and a hematopoietic medulla hyperplasia, indicative of a physiological answer to an aggressive situation.

This *criboso* or porous syndrome constitutes a “systemic hiperostotic osteoporosis” or that of multi-

		IN SITU	ISOLATED
CARIES	Permanents	7	3
	Deciduals	0	2
HYPOPLASIA	Permanents	21	19
	Deciduals	0	0

Table 4. Results of the Dental Caries and Enamel Hypoplasia Study

	CALCULUS		
	slight	Moderate	severe
Permanents Isolated	21	5	1
Permanents in situ	55	15	0
Percentage	46,6	12,3	0,6

Table 5. Results of the Dental Tartar Study

ple localization. However, its apparition is not always constant or the same in all the individuals. It points out that in the genesis, certain idiosyncratic physiopathology aspects should prevail.

Multipopulation studies and of isolated and control cases indicate that these porous lesions appear developing in the sinus of a "mature bone" with a great answer capacity. However, these porosities do not appear in all the infantile-juvenile individuals. Then, they do not correspond to a constant physiological situation. That is to say, the presence of a morbid or aggressive fact is what develops the porous answer in the immature bone sinus and in specific localizations of hemathopoietic medulla's greater activity. It can also show localizations with a great bone length growth activity that obviously requires a great sanguineous or oligoelement contribution.

With regard to the etiological hypothesis referring to the *cribra orbitalia*, they are considered to be multiple (Stuart-Macadam, 1985, 1987, 1989, 1991, 1992, 1996). *Cribra Orbitalia* has been associated with acquired ferropenic anemia, Cooley Mediterranean thalassemia, G6PDH deficit, parasitic infections, child-birth or menstruation sanguineous loss, malnutrition, bad hygienic-sanitary conditions, hypovitaminosis, malabsorption syndrome in poor ferrous diet; increase in the ferrous necessities during growth, etc...

Recent studies carried out by us in Wistar laboratory rats (Polo, M.; Miquel, M. and Villalain, J. D., 1999a) are highly significant, for they have let us experimentally reproduce lesions compatible with *cribra orbitalia*. They demonstrate that the *cribra orbitalia* etiopathogenia (and by extension, the rest of the porous phenomenology) is related to ferropenic and hypomagnesemia anemia, associated with infantile stress (precocious weaning). This ambient "paleopathological quandary" is the result of an anemic process associated with malnutrition and/or gastrointestinal illnesses that entail Mg (among other elements) absorption deficit.

	SLIMMING OF ALVEOLAR BONE		
	slight	moderate	severe
Permanents in situ	34	20	11
Deciduals in situ	2	5	0
% dientes in situ con periodontitis	31,8	22,1	9,7

Table 6. Results of the Alveolar Bone Reduction Study (Periodontal Illness)

So the porous osteoarchaeological syndrome constitutes a paleonutritional indicator in which there is a participation of three etiological situations, isolated or in association, experimentally demonstrated: ferropenic anemia, malabsorption and precocious weaning.

In its etiology three physiopathological situations are interlaced:

1. An increase of nutritive necessities, typical of the infancy and youth.
2. A pathological malnutrition process of caloric-protein malnutrition with malabsorption syndrome, associated with repetition infections (gastrointestinal parasitic) and ferropenic anemias.
3. An inadequate dietary ingesta.

As it has been experimentally demonstrated, Mg and Fe have a special etiopathogenic role in *cribra orbitalia* and in the porous experimental orbitalia. In total agreement with these results, other authors (Sandford M. K.; Van Gerven D. P. and Meglen R. R., 1983) find deficits of these oligoelements in human remains affected by *cribra orbitalia*. Concretely, these analysis are carried out in hair samples of mummified human remains, affected by *cribra*.

Figure 2. Abscess with Buccal Drainage in an Adult Individual

Paleopathological Morphological Paleonutritional Indicators: rachitis?

Another finding, not thoroughly clarified in nature, is the excessive curvature femoral shaft, in anteroposterior course, in all the infantile-juvenile individuals. Some authors (Rodríguez J. V., 1994) indicate that it is typical of vitamin deficit (rachitis).

Anthropometric Morphological Paleonutritional Indicators

Height

Height, plactinemy and platymery have been studied in all the remains. With regard to the calculation of height, it was established from the measurements of the tables 7 and 8.

As it can be observed, men's height oscillate between 162 and 179 cm, and the women's height between 144 and 151 cm.

The poor conservation state of the remains has not allowed us to establish clear physical typologies. Apart from the absence of complete skulls, it is added the fragmentation of postcranial skeletons and the impossibility of individualize adults is added. Even these limitations, it is possible to compare the height obtained in our study with other European Neolithic

Populations. The mid height of the studied population, just considering the full bones, is of 166,3 cm. This figure is lower than the Beddoe British Series that establishes a middle height from femurs, of 171,8 cm, using the Trotter and Gleser formula. In Franco-Belgium populations and starting from femorotibial height measurements, the result is of 167,8 cm, also higher than the measurements we have found (Wells, 1969).

Platycnemia / Platymery

There is a presence of platycnemia in all the tibias, except one; and platymery in all the femurs. The platycnemia consists of a transversal flattening of tibial shafts. The anemic indexes obtained are: 51'2; 53'6; 61'3; 62'2; 65'7, and 72'7. The calculated platymeric indexes are: 75; 76'6; 81'8.

Platymery and platycnemia are related, among other causes, to nutritional deficits.

Biochemical Paleonutritional Indicators

The quantitative analysis of oligoelement or sketch elements content in the bone is a paleoanthropological use technique that allows to characterize the human populations' diets, and it is based on the trophic division suffered by some elements (Sr, Ba, Zn, Cu) and in relation with human and animal Ca (herbivorous,

Figure 3. Porous Archaeological Morphological, Radiological, and Histopathological Syndrome Case Study in the Villanueva de la Fuente Bury.

omnivorous, carnivorous), while Zn increases along that chain.

A quantitative analysis of Ca, Sr and Zn has been carried out to be able to discriminate the feeding economy kind. Concretely Sr is a herbivorous diet indicator while Zn is a carnivorous diet. The loss of skeleton anatomic connection has made possible to carry out an individualized analytical study according to sex and age. In the same way, important deterioration of infantile human remains has made impossible the oligoelements study, due to the important taphonomic and diagenetic influence.

Nevertheless, seven bone samples, representative of the adult populations, have been analyzed in order to obtain general data of human group oligoelements. Each sample corresponded to the diaphysary, femoral or humeral compact osseous tissue (of a young adult individual), and with an approximate weight of 3 gr/sample.

The used technique has been the X Ray Fluorescence (XRF), thanks to the infrastructure of the Experimental Research Support Central Service (SCSIE) from Valencia University. The XRF is an analysis technique whose method, still not much used in paleodiet studies (Ahlgren L., *et al.* 1981; Safont S., 1992 mention by Malgosa A. and Subirá M. E., 1997), is to radiate the substance (in this case, an amount of pulverized bone) with a X Ray Beam, at an adequate energy. After that, to analyze the wavelength of the excited characteristics radiation of elements present in the substance by using a spectrometer. The advantage of this method is that it is not destructive in comparison to the A. A. S. The apparatus used is the model PW 2400 Philips, coupled to the software Super Q Manager, with two analytical possibilities: quantitative and qualitative/semiquantitative.

The used analysis protocol is the one we suggested and has been successfully used in other osseous collections (Polo M., *et al.* 1999b; Miquel; Polo and Villalain 1999a) and consists of:

1. Cleaning the sample with milliQ water during 5 minutes.
2. Ultrasonic seried baths during 15 minutes in order to attenuate the diagenetic process.
3. Desiccation in stove at 125°C during 5 minutes.
4. Bone fragmentation in an initial sample.
5. Weight of the initial sample.
6. Calcination of the sample at 850°C during 45 minutes.
7. Cooling in dryer during 10 minutes.
8. Weight of the sample.
9. Bone pulverization, to be analyzed through XRF.

The analyzed samples belong to seven human beings (young adults), two herbivorous (*oryctolagus cuniculus*) and one of soil from the bed.

The results obtained in the human remains are the following: Ca (mg/gr)=358,67 (DS 4.7), Sr (ppm) =157,28 (DS37,1), and Zn (ppm)=142,62 (DS 58,3).

The interpretation of these results has been done following the system established by Fornaciari, G. and Mallegni, F. (1987). This system classifies the human populations' economical or feeding pattern based on Zn and Sr in-bone concentration as regards Ca (See table 9).

These authors establish some limit values of index Sr/Ca (corrected) = Sr/Ca human / Sr/Ca herbivorous (O. R., observed ratio) and of index Zn/Ca to classify the human group diet.

The obtained results for both indexes are: Sr/Ca (c) = Sr/Ca human / Sr/Ca oryctologus curriculum = 0,843 (O. R., observed ratio) and Zn/Ca = 0,397.

Following the mentioned authors' proposals for inter-

BONE	SEX	LENGTH (MM)	HEIGHT (CM)
Humerus	Male	303	163-164
Humerus	Male	313	166-167
Tibiae	Male	382	174-175
Femur	Female	392	151
Radius	Male	236	168-169
Radius	Male	231	166-167
Radius	Male	231	166-167
Ulna	Male	256	168-169
Ulna	Male	258	168-170
Ulna	Male	257	169

Table 7. Height Calculation Results (1)

BONE	SEX M / F	FRAGMENT LENGTH (MM)	LENGTH PERCENTAGE	LENGTH BONE (MM)	HEIGHT (CM)
Humerus	F	32	11,73	272,8	149-150
Humerus	F	33	11,73	281,3	150-151
Humerus	F	32	11,73	272,8	149-150
Humerus	M	36	11,73	306,9	164-165
Humerus	M	37	11,73	315,4	167-168
Humerus	M	35	11,73	298,4	162-163
Tibiae	M	20	5,03	397,4	178-179
Radius	F	27	14,31	188,6	144
Radius	M	37	14,31	258,5	176-177
Radius	M	19	7,46	254,7	175-176

Table 8. Height Calculation Results (2)

pretation, the index Sr/Ca (O. R. = 0,84) suggests a kind of vegetarian agricultural feeding, with a protein contribution of medium animal origin (Zn/Ca = 0,39).

Radiological Paleonutritional Indicators

Any of the mentioned radiological signs have been found, indicative of nutritional origin pathological

DIET PATTERN	O.R. (Sr/Ca CALIBRATE)
Agricultural (vegetarian)	>0.7
Mixed (vegetable, milk, meat)	0.4-0.7
Pastoral (milk, meat)	<0.4
CARNIC INGESTION PATTERN	Zn/Ca
Rich (meta and milk)	>0.5
Midle (vegetable, milk, meat)	0.35-0.5
Little (vegetable)	<0.35

Table 9. System of Oligoelements Analysis Interpretation with Paleonutritional Purposes.

process. Specially, taphonomical alteration of infantile–juvenile remains has conditioned these studies.

Demographic Paleonutritional Indicators

The finding of twelve adult left ulnas allowed us to assign this number as the minimal number to adult population. This figure corresponds to the minimal number of five women (five female skulls) and seven men (seven left ulnas and seven male right radios). It was possible to assign the subadult to seven individuals. Thus, we have a 19 individuals population, a minimal number of twelve adults and seven subadults.

Next we are going to present the bioanthropological study of infantile–juvenile individuals and adults, in separate ways.

Infantile and Subadults

Next (See Table 10), the anthropological data of subadult skeletons is presented:

AGE (YEARS)	SEX (POSIBLE)	HEIGHT (CM)
Neonatos - 6 meses	----	50-64
4-5	Female	915-974
5-6	Male	988-1047
6-7	Female	1103-1146
7-8	Male	1105-1162
11-12	Male	1330-1385
15-16	Male	1546-1594

Table 10. Demography of Infantile – Juvenile Population Group

Adults

Next (see Table 11), the Bioanthropological Data of Adults Skeletons is presented:

	MALE	FEMALE	ALOFISO	TOTAL
Cranium	1	5	1	7
Pelvis	2	1		3
Humerus	6	4	1	11
Tibiae	4	3		7
Femur	6	2		8
Ulna	7	5		12
Radius	7	3	2	12

Table 11. Demography of the Adult Population Group

In general, it is possible to say that this study is about young adults, because the cranial furrows remain permeable and just degenerative signs in 8 vertebraes, three kneecap and a calcaneus were observed.

Preliminary Study of Faunal Remains

About two hundred of faunal remains belonging to that bed have been microscopically studied, by means of a binocular magnifying glass. The preliminary study indicates the presence of abundant wild herbivorous fauna of *oryctolagus cuniculus* kind (rabbit) and *crapahircus* (goat). In addition but in less proportion, small rodent mandibular remains have been found.

The presence of abundant osseous remains, specially the *oryctolagus cuniculus* that present fresh bone typical fractures at a diaphysary level, is surprising. It is about oblique fractures with cutting and waving edges, and with soft surfaces. Some of these fractures permit to aim a human action mechanism to be able to extract the bone medulla or marrow.

Other faunal remains presented small incisions between 3 and 5 mm length in the diaphysary surface. But most of these tracks aim to a taphonomic pseudopathology because of roots due to their localization in bones, specially disqualified and highly affected by environmental phenomena. This mainly aims to a taphonomic pseudopathology by roots action. However, most of these pieces are still under study.

These figures show that most of these faunal remains were probably feeding support of the studied human group.

Conclusions

Paleonutritional aspects of a population that lived during the IV millennium BC in *Ciudad Real* (Spain) have been studied. It is about a young people group with high infantile mortality and middle hope of life under 40 years.

Demographically, it is impossible to say that there is a predominant sex.

The average population height is similar to the European populations from the same epoch.

The osseous study of infantile–juvenile remains allows to state the possibility of finding a vitamin nutritional lack (possibly rachitis) as the basic of an excessive curvature presence of femoral diaphysis in the antero-posterior in all these individuals, as well as the high enamel hypoplasia incidence.

There is a low caries incidence and antemortem dental loss, and a high periodontal illness incidence, dental calculus and enamel hypoplasia. The abrasion degree

is light-moderate.

The faunal remains study allows to point out that certain feeding economy was based on wild rabbit and goat herbivorous.

The oligoelements analysis suggests a kind of agricultural feeding, rich in carbohydrates, with a proteins contribution of medium animal origin.

The finding of a skeleton with *cribra orbitalia* associated to a femur cribra, suggests that this individual suffered from an anemic process associated to a malnutrition or another gastrointestinal pathology, that provoke an absorption deficit or a ferrous and magnesium lack.

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Elisa García Prósper and Miguel Sáez for their support in the graphic work. To all the researchers from the Anthropology and Paleopathology Laboratory, Legal Medicine Teaching Unit, Medicine School, University of Valencia (Spain).

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